

Average alcohol consumption among patients diagnosed with liver cirrhosis: A cross-sectional analysis

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Abstract

Background: Alcohol-related liver cirrhosis is a leading cause of chronic liver disease worldwide. Risk and progression are dose-dependent and influenced by exposure duration and sex-specific susceptibility.

Aim: To evaluate the quantity and duration of alcohol consumption in patients with alcohol-related liver cirrhosis.

Materials and methods: In this prospective cross-sectional study (January 2022–December 2025), 548 adults with alcohol-related cirrhosis (Child–Pugh classes A–C) hospitalized at the University Emergency Hospital “Pirogov,” Sofia, were included. Alcohol intake was self-reported and converted to grams of pure ethanol per week.

Results: The mean weekly intake was 339.66 g of ethanol (28.3 standard drinks). The mean duration of consumption before diagnosis was 107.72 ± 28.84 months. Alcohol intake differed significantly across Child–Pugh classes ($F = 6.62$, $p < 0.001$), with the highest consumption in Child C. Duration of intake was also significantly associated with quantity consumed ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Patients with alcohol-related cirrhosis demonstrate sustained high alcohol intake over prolonged periods. Greater consumption and longer exposure are significantly associated with more severe hepatic impairment.

Keywords

alcohol consumption, alcoholic liver disease, Child–Pugh classification, ethanol, liver cirrhosis

Introduction

Liver cirrhosis represents the final common pathway of chronic liver injury (Hosseini et al. 2019). While multiple etiologies (viral, metabolic, autoimmune) exist, alcohol consumption remains one of the leading causes worldwide (Dos Santos et al. 2018). The impact of alcohol on liver disease is dose-dependent, multifactorial, and influenced by genetic, metabolic, and environmental factors (Aberg et al. 2022).

Alcohol (ethanol) is metabolized in hepatocytes to acetaldehyde and reactive oxygen species, inducing oxidative stress, inflammatory signaling, stellate cell activation, and extracellular matrix deposition. The pathological progression typically follows steatosis (fatty liver), alcoholic hepatitis, fibrosis, and ultimately cirrhosis (Hsu and Kowdley 2016). This sequence reflects a cumulative injury process in which continued alcohol use exacerbates hepatic inflammation (Hsu and Kowdley 2016). Women have a lower tolerance to alcohol-induced liver injury than men, likely due to reduced aldehyde dehydrogenase activity and hormonal effects, contributing to earlier cirrhosis at lower intake levels (Huang et al. 2023). Alcohol use is a major contributor to cirrhosis globally. Approximately 25% of global cirrhosis deaths are alcohol-associated, with increasing per capita alcohol consumption projected in the coming decades (Llamosas-Falcón et al. 2024).

Meta-analyses demonstrate that low to moderate occasional drinking may not significantly alter cirrhosis risk, moderate daily drinking increases risk, especially in women, and heavy consumption (≥ 5 drinks/day) dramatically elevates cirrhosis risk (Rehm et al. 2010).

Systematic reviews confirm a dose-dependent increase in cirrhosis risk with rising alcohol levels. Women face a higher relative risk compared to men at similar exposure (Rehm et al. 2010; Roerecke et al. 2019).

In patients with chronic hepatitis B, alcohol showed a linear dose-dependent increase in cirrhosis risk: every additional 12 g of alcohol per day (~ 1 drink) was associated with a round 6.2% increase in cirrhosis risk compared with non-drinkers. This modeling approach shows that even relatively low intakes incrementally raise cirrhosis risk (Wu et al. 2025).

In earlier systematic reviews, occasional drinking had no significantly increased risk. One drink/day (12 g) increased cirrhosis risk in women (but not significantly in men), reflecting sex-specific vulnerability (Savolainen et al. 1993; Rehm et al. 2010). More than 5 drinks per day (≥ 60 g) were associated with substantially higher relative

risks, with women showing much larger increases than men (Savolainen et al. 1993; Rehm et al. 2010).

Studies usually define one standard drink as 12 g (15.2 mL) of pure ethanol. This allows comparison across research (Wu et al. 2025).

Materials and methods

This prospective cross-sectional study was conducted from January 2022 to December 2025 at the University Emergency Hospital “Pirogov,” Sofia, Bulgaria. A total of 548 adult patients diagnosed with alcohol-related liver cirrhosis were included. Some patients were hospitalized more than once during the study period; however, each individual was analyzed once. Over four years, all 548 patients were surveyed to mark the quantity of alcohol intake and the period of alcohol intake before being diagnosed with liver cirrhosis. The data are based on the answers provided in the survey. The patients were male and female between the ages of 20 and 88 years.

Inclusion criteria were the following: (1) male and non-pregnant female subjects, (2) age over 18 years at the time of first hospitalization, (3) diagnosis of liver cirrhosis with alcoholic etiology – Child–Pugh score A, B, or C, (4) willingness to answer questions about alcohol intake.

Exclusion criteria were the following: (1) history or serology for hepatitis B or C, (2) other hepatotropic viruses, (3) autoimmune diseases, (4) oncological diseases, (5) use of hepatotoxic medication, (6) history of peptic, gallbladder, or other abdominal surgery, (7) pregnancy or breastfeeding, (8) denial of alcohol use. Every subject had to make a self-assessment of alcohol intake, and the result was calculated as pure ethanol quantity per week, and the period was calculated in months.

The results of the study were processed using the PSPP program. The quantitative data were investigated with descriptive statistics and linear regression, and graphical visualization was used.

Results

A total of 548 subjects were surveyed; of them, 413 were males (75.4%) and 135 were females (24.6%). The minimum age was 20 years, and the maximum age was 88 years at the moment of assessment, with a mean age of 57.20 ± 11.98 years. The descriptive statistics by sex and age are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Data by sex and age.

Sex	Statistic of age	Value	Std. error
Male	Mean	56.79	0.59
	Median	56.00	
	Std. deviation	12.07	
	Minimum	24.00	
	Maximum	88.00	
	Range	64.00	
	Interquartile range	18.00	
Female	Mean	58.44	1.00
	Median	58.00	
	Std. deviation	11.66	
	Minimum	20.00	
	Maximum	86.00	
	Range	66.00	
	Interquartile range	15.00	

The data for alcohol intake were evaluated as the volume of pure ethanol per week. The minimum quantity was assessed by the subjects to be 200 mL per week, and the maximum quantity was assessed to be 760 mL per week. The mean pure alcohol intake was 430.5 mL per week, which is 339.66 g. If one standard drink is 12 g, the result is 28.30 drinks per week or 4.04 drinks per day for the whole sample. These results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Alcohol intake data.

Alcohol intake data	Alcohol (ml per week)
Mean intake weekly (pure ethanol)	430.50
Std. deviation	105.38
Minimum	200.00
Maximum	760.00

The distribution curve of the results shown in Table 2 is visualized in Fig. 1. It is clearly shown that the maximum frequency is between 300 and 500 mL alcohol intake.

The period of alcohol intake is another factor. The subjects with a very high quantity of alcohol intake show a shortened period before diagnosis. The mean period is 107.72 months. The minimum is 36 months, and the maximum is 182 months.

Figure 1. Distribution curve for alcohol intake.

The minimal period for males is 60 months, and the minimum for females is 36 months. For the mean period for both groups, there are no significant differences. The scatterplot visualization of alcohol intake versus period is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Scatterplot visualization for quantity of alcohol intake versus period in months.

The range and the median, expressed separately for males and females, indicate higher values of alcohol intake in mL for males versus lower values for females. These results are graphically shown in Fig. 3, and the values are presented in Table 3.

Figure 3. Alcohol intake for males and females.

Table 3. Alcohol intake for males and females.

	Sex	Statistic	Value	Std. error
mL per week	Male	Mean	444.90	5.14
		Median	440.00	
		Std. deviation	104.39	
		Minimum	200.00	
		Maximum	760.00	
	Female	Mean	386.44	8.27
		Median	360.00	
		Std. deviation	96.07	
		Minimum	200.00	
		Maximum	750.00	

Alcohol consumption has some differences according to Child–Pugh score. Both the mean and the median are higher in Child B subjects than in Child A and higher in Child B subjects than in Child C. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Alcohol consumption in different Child–Pugh scores.

	Child score	Statistic	Value	Std. error
ml per week	Child A	Mean	354.73	8.67
		Median	345.00	
		Std. deviation	74.09	
		Minimum	200.00	
		Maximum	620.00	
	Child B	Mean	395.37	6.25
		Median	380.00	
		Std. deviation	91.37	
		Minimum	200.00	
		Maximum	750.00	
	Child C	Mean	480.50	6.15
		Median	480.00	
		Std. deviation	99.32	
		Minimum	260.00	
		Maximum	760.00	

A boxplot (box-and-whisker plot) visually summarizes the distribution of a continuous dataset of alcohol consumption using five key statistics: the minimum, first quartile, median, third quartile, and maximum in all Child–Pugh score patients. It highlights the data center, spread, skewness, and outliers via a central box and extending whiskers. The distribution is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Alcohol consumption in different Child–Pugh scores.

To predict a connection between Child–Pugh score and alcohol consumption based on alcohol intake as various factors, linear regression (analysis of variance, ANOVA) was used. Child scores differ across the 47 groups of alcohol intake. Variation between group means is 6.62 times larger than variation within groups, which is quite substantial. The p -value shows a highly statistically significant result. The results are shown in Table 5.

To predict a connection between the period of alcohol consumption and the quantity of alcohol consumption,

Table 5. Linear regression between Child–Pugh score as the dependent variable and alcohol intake as a factor.

ANOVA		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Significance
Child score	Between Groups	101.88	46	2.21	6.62	$p < 0.001$
	Within Groups	167.62	501	0.33		
	Total	269.50	547			

linear regression (analysis of variance, ANOVA) was used. Between-group variability is 3.32 times larger than within-group variability. The result is statistically significant – $p < 0.001$. The result is shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Linear regression between alcohol intake period as the dependent variable and alcohol intake as a factor.

ANOVA		Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Significance
Intake months	Between Groups	127159.5	46	2764.34	3.32	$p < 0.001$
	Within Groups	416940.4	501	832.22		
	Total	544099.8	547			

The total mortality for the period is 9.3% (51 cases).

Discussion

In this cross-sectional analysis, a very high alcohol consumption rate is detected in patients with liver cirrhosis with ethanol etiology. The average weekly consumption is 430.50 mL pure ethanol, which is 339.66 g. If we use 12 g alcohol as a standard drink, we could evaluate an average rate of 4.04 drinks daily. The rate is higher for the male subjects. The difference between male and female mean consumption is 58.46 mL pure ethanol. Because the methodology involves self-assessment, it is possible for the real rates to be even higher. The maximum of 760.00 mL weekly and the average of 430.50 mL weekly show that patients with liver cirrhosis with alcohol etiology have alcohol consumption that is much higher than the quantity designated as toxic in the literature – 8.1 to 13.3 drinks weekly (Aberg et al. 2022). The mean alcohol consumption period of 107.72 months and the distribution of quantity of alcohol for the period show that subjects with liver cirrhosis often have a history of systematic consumption of more than 8 years. It is very likely that patients with liver cirrhosis who deny alcohol intake and are suspected of alcohol use actually consume particularly large amounts of alcohol.

Apart from gender differences, there are differences between patients with different Child–Pugh scores. The consumption in more severe cirrhosis is expectedly higher. The linear regression test (ANOVA) shows very high statistical significance of the presented results.

Limitations include reliance on self-reported intake and the single-center design.

Conclusion

Patients with alcoholic liver cirrhosis seem to have a very high quantity of alcohol consumption for years. Patients with liver cirrhosis have, on average, more than 28 standard drinks weekly for more than 8 years. Higher intake with a longer period predicts more severe liver impairment. An average 58 mL lower weekly alcohol intake in females predicts the same liver injury as the higher alcohol intake in males.

It is highly likely that most patients with alcoholic liver cirrhosis have a history of similar alcohol intake, although some deny use. Early detection of high-risk drinking patterns remains essential for prevention strategies.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

Clinical trials: EK-01-26/05.02.2026.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: University Multidisciplinary Hospital for Active Treatment and Emergency Medicine "N. I. Pirogov", Sofia, Bulgaria.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.